

Event Abstract

Effect of cell phone radiation on behavior and reproductive system in male albino mice

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Radiation can be classified as ionized or non-ionized radiation. Non-ionizing and electromagnetic radiation consist of electromagnetic waves that are not active enough to separate electrons from atoms or molecules, and therefore cannot lead to their ionization. This include radio waves, microwaves. Cell phone is type of radio waves have wavelengths in the electromagnetic spectrum longer up to 300 GHz. Aim of work is to study of the effect of radiation of cell phone on the behavior and male reproductive system in albino mice (histological study). Methodology: Twelve male albino mice were divided into two groups (n=6). One group as control (healthy mice), the second group were exposed to cell phone radiation one hour/day for three months. At the end of experiment, behavior scoring using plus maze and force swimming maze was applied for the two groups. Mice were killed by cervical dislocation, and dissected. The testis, cauda epididymis and vasa deferentia collected; seminal fluid collected for sperm count, motility and morphology. Testis were kept in formalin for histological examination. Results and conclusion: Behavior study using plus maze and forced swimming maze did not show any changes after exposure to cell phone radiation for three months. There was a significant increase in abnormal sperm count compared to the control. In histological study, healthy mice showed normal seminiferous tubule lumen full of mature spermatozoa, complete spermatogenesis, normal histological features of seminiferous tubules, normal seminiferous tubules separated from each other by narrow interstitial spaces containing interstitial of Leydig cell, seminiferous tubules containing spermatogenic cells and Sertoli cells, and normal spermatogenic cells were formed of

spermatogonia, primary spermatocytes and spermatids. Cell phone radiation exposed mice showed a reduction of intraluminal spermatozoa, hypospermatogenic cells of seminiferous tubules, sperms were very few inside the lumen of seminiferous tubules; also, there was a reduced number spermatogonia, spermatocytes, spermatid, and Sertoli cells. It can be concluded that the radiation of the cell phone may produce damage to the reproductive system.

Keywords: Cell phone radiation, Male mice, Reproductive system, Plus maze, Swimming maze.

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